

Any cell may act like a TV and produce image

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Abstract: Each cell may have the ability to act like a TV device and produce some images and photos. DNAs are formed from charged particles that by their motions, some waves are emerged. They are built from hexagonal and pentagonal bases which could play the role of planes within electronic capacitors. Also, they are coiled several times around different axes and form several inductors. These capacitors and inductors may join to each other and form resonance circuits which emit or receive different frequencies. These waves may shoot electrons and other charges toward phosphoric layers within phospholipids. By colliding charges and phosphors, maybe, some light points are formed. These points may join to each other and form some real images within cells. If this theory be true, each image which is emerged within the eye could be converted to currents, transformed to brain and then to all cells. Then, DNAs emit related waves and these waves shoot electrons and ions towards phosphors within phospholipids and other cellular elements and produce light points and images. We can test this theory for microbes. Micro-organisms see the shape of light source and may build some shapes like it. Also, microbes under a microscope may diagnose some objects on the eye object and interact with them. Because, a microscope not only produce big images of microbes, but build small images for microbes of macro-objects.

Keywords: Cells, TV, DNA, Capacitors, Inductors, Circuit, Microbes

I. Introduction

Up to date, it has been known that micro-organisms like bacteria show some quantum effects and use of quantum channels for exchanging information with each other and medium. Some of them like magnetotactic bacteria, caple bacteria, photosynthetic bacteria, luminous bacteria and exoelectrogenic bacteria have

special structures and could emit or absorb quantum particles like photons and electrons. Some others have no special antenna; however, their structures are formed from charged particles and consequently, by motions of these charges, some currents are emerged. These currents could exchange waves with any external biological and non-biological currents. Among bacteria with special structures; we can refer to magnetotactic bacteria which could exchange quantum electromagnetic waves with medium. Magnetotactic bacteria (or MTB) are a polyphyletic group of bacteria that orient themselves along the magnetic field lines of Earth's magnetic field and also other magnetic fields[1]. Magnetotactic bacteria (MTB) have the unique ability to produce magnetic particles surrounded by a biomembrane to form the magnetosome organelle. Therefore, MTB have novel physical and magnetic properties and have consequently been used in several biotechnological applications. For example, they could be used to generate electricity based on Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction [2]. Another example is the cable bacteria which conduct electricity across distances over 1 cm in sediment and groundwater aquifers and connect electron donors to electron acceptors [3]. In addition to these two groups, there is a third group of photosynthetic bacteria like purple [4] and Cyanobacteria [5,6] that are phototrophic, capable of producing their own food and energy via photosynthesis. Furthermore, Bioluminescent bacteria are another type of bacteria which produce light. These bacteria are predominantly present in sea water, marine sediments, the surface of decomposing fish and in the gut of marine animals [7]. And finally, exoelectrogenic bacteria are another main micro-organisms which have the ability to transfer electrons extracellularly [8]. Besides these special bacteria, normal bacteria also exchange quantum particles with medium. For example, some authors have disclosed that 460–470 nm light-emitting diode could inhibit the growth of some bacteria like *E. coli*. Their study has shown that bacterial growth inhibition by LED was more effective at 4 °C than at 25 °C [9]. In another work, researchers have reported effects of light-dark cycles on photosynthetic bacteria wastewater treatment and valuable substances production. Their results have asserted that 24 h light/24 h dark cycle led the best biomass production and 3h light/3h dark cycle led the highest protein [10]. In another investigation, it has been demonstrated that exposing *L. acidophilus* and *L. Casei* probiotic bacteria to radiofrequency electromagnetic radiation (RF-EMF) of Wi-Fi router show significantly increased proliferation and lactic acid production [11].

In addition to bacteria, there are other biological objects like chloroplasts and micro-bubbles which use of quantum particles for exchanging information with medium. Chloroplasts which play the main role in photosynthesis, could absorb quantum photons from medium and send quantum charges like H^+ , electrons and other particles to extracellular space [12]. On the other hand, micro-bubbles are biological objects which are formed from water molecules, gases and charged ions and can be formed around micro-organisms like bacteria and viruses. These micro-bubbles could be collapsed by ultrasound waves and some quantum photons are produced. These photons may play the main role in destruction/growth or any other evolutions of micro-organisms like bacteria [13,14].

Now, the question arises that how micro-organisms diagnose light waves and interact with them? In previous results, several mechanisms have been proposed which in non of them, the process of formation of image hasn't considered. In this research, we discuss a hypothesis that maybe, some images of medium is emerged within the cellular nucleus and also microbial membranes.

The outline of this paper is as follows: In section II, we propose the model. In section III, we discuss the method. In section IV, we bring the result. The last sections devoted to discussion and conclusion.

II. The model

In this section, we will show that matters within a cell act like elements of a TV and could produce different images in each second. In a TV, there are some circuits which take or radiate some waves with different frequencies. These waves could force to electrons and shoot them towards a phosphoric layers. These collidings have different intensities and produce some special light points. These points join to each other and form an image. Now, we can describe the similar process within a cell (See figure 1) :

1. A DNA is formed from charged particles which by their motions within a cell, some waves are emerged.

2. A DNA is formed from hexagonal-pentagonal bases. These bases could join to each other and form some capacitors. The capacity in each capacity is different and may store a wave with frequency f_i .
3. A DNA is compacted several times and produce several inductors. Each inductor may moves and emit a special wave with frequency of f_i .
4. DNA capacitors and inductors may join to each other and form several resonance circuits. These circuits emit waves with different frequencies:

$$\text{Wave}_i = A_i \sin (2\pi [\lambda_i]^{-1} (x-x_i)-2\pi f_i (t-t_i)) + B_i \cos (2\pi [\lambda_i]^{-1} (x-x_i)-2\pi f_i (t-t_i))$$

5. These waves may join to each other and form total DNA waves.

$$\text{DNA waves} = \text{Sum}_{i=1}^{i=N} (\text{Wave}_i) = \text{Sum}_{i=1}^{i=N} (A_i \sin (2\pi [\lambda_i]^{-1} (x-x_i)-2\pi f_i (t-t_i)) + B_i \cos (2\pi [\lambda_i]^{-1} (x-x_i)-2\pi f_i (t-t_i)))$$

6. From other side, emitted waves from a DNA could interact with charges around it and force them to move towards phosphoric layers within phospholipids. By colliding these charges, some light points are emerged. These points join to each other and form some images within the nucleus of cells.

Above mechanism may be not limited to human cells and could be applied within other micro-organisms so. We bring some results which may be the signature of formation of images within the structure of microbes.

Figure 1: Formation of Image within nucleuses

III. Material and method

III-A: Material:

1. Microscope
2. Multigonal lamp
3. A metal-glass slide
4. Leaf cells
5. Water and oil

III-B: Method:

- 1: A leaf is divided into several parts and put some sugar-like matters on it.
2. These leaf parts may be put on a metal-glass slide.
3. A multi-gonal lamp could be put instead of light source under a 100x lens of microscope.
4. Slide could be put under the 100x objective lens and observe the evolutions of microbes (See figure 2).
5. An object could be put on one of eye lenses and consider evolutions of microbes by using both lenses (See figure 3).

Figure 2. Microbes see the shape of light source

Fig 3: Microbes diagnose macro-organisms and objects

IV. Results:

1. Microbes on a glass-metal slide see changes in light source and try to form some colonies which its shape is similar to lightening lamp . For example, for a multi-gonal lamp, microbes build several multigonal colonies (See figures 4 and 5).
2. Metal in a metal-gold slide could be useful in conducting microbes. Because, light waves cause to motion of charges and formation of multi-gonal charged shapes. On the other hand, some microbes observe evolutions of charges and for eating and absorbing them, try to become close them and form multi-gonal shapes.
3. We put an object on one of eye lenses and consider evolutions of microbes under both lenses. It is wonderful that A. Microbes interact with the object on the eye lens. B. Under the eye lens without object, one can observe that below of the object is approximately empty of microbes. This seems that microscope see that object. Maybe, a

microscope make objects small and in the size of microbes for them such as it makes microbes big for us (Compare figures 6 and 7).

Fig 4. Building multi-gonal colonies of microbes and micro-bubbles by a multi-gonal source (First picture)

Fig 5. Building multi-gonal colonies of microbes and micro-bubbles by a multi-gonal source (Second picture)

Figure 6: An object on one of eye lenses

Figure 7: Second eye lens without any object

Discussion:

Up to date, it has been known that the process of seeing is done by the help of eye cells and formation of images within eye . However, eye cells are formed during some evolutions of stem cells within an embryo. When, sperms and eggs are fused and initial cells of an embryo is formed, some genes conduct process and form specialized cells like eye ones. Thus, the mechanism of seeing first is programmed within stem cells at initial stages of an embryo. On other hand, a question is always existed? After formation of initial image within the eye, what occurs and this image is transformed to where? Maybe, one response that this image could be sent to the brain and stored in its memory. However, we can assume that there is another probability so. Maybe, this image not only is stored in memory of brain but is transformed to at least special cells and stored as some frequencies in some genetic resonance circuits (See figure 8).

Figure 8: Image waves are transformed from a brain to all or at least special cells.

Conclusion:

This research has proposed a new proposal for interaction between electromagnetic waves and cells. In this proposal, genetic circuits within cells are formed from biological capacitors and inductors. These elements exchange currents and emit some photons with different frequencies. These photons force on charges and shoot them towards phosphor layers within phospholipids. These charges collide with phosphors and produce some lichening points. By joining these points, some images are formed. Maybe, microbes use of this mechanism to observe objects. For

example, it seems that microbes see evolutions of light source and also detect the existence of some things on an eye lens under a microscope.

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